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**Effects of calcium salts of palm fatty acids on nutrient digestibility and
production responses of lactating dairy cows:
a meta-analysis and meta-regression**

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INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY

Effects of calcium salts of palm fatty acids on nutrient digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows: a meta-analysis and meta-regression. *By dos Santos Neto et al., page XXX.* Our objective was to perform a meta-analysis and meta-regression to evaluate the effects of calcium salts of palm fatty acids on nutrient digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows. Also, we aimed to evaluate whether experimental design impacts production responses to supplementation with calcium salts of palm fatty acids. Our results indicate no reason for the restrictive use of change-over designs in supplementation studies and meta-analysis with calcium salts of palm fatty acids. Feeding calcium salts of palm fatty acids reduced dry matter intake and increased the yields of milk and milk fat.

Supplemental Table S1. List of the studies used in the data set and their experimental designs.

Authors	Year	Reported design ¹	Design type ²	
			Continuous	Change-over
Schneider et al.	1988	SRD/CBD	X	X
Kent and Arambel	1988	CRD	X	
Schauff and Clark	1989	LSD		X
Canale et al.	1990	LSD		X
Andrew et al.	1991	SRD		X
Sklan et al.	1991	CBD	X	
Erickson et al.	1992	CRD	X	
Sklan et al.	1992	CBD	X	
Holter et al.	1992	CRD	X	
Schauff et al.	1992	LSD		X
Schauff and Clark	1992	LSD		X
Spicer et al.	1993	CRD	X	
Wu et al.	1993	CBD	X	
Salfer et al.	1994	CRD	X	
Sklan et al.	1994	CBD	X	
Simas et al.	1995	CBD	X	
Harrison et al.	1995	CBD	X	
Beaulieu and Palmquist	1995	CRD	X	
Cervantes et al.	1996	CBD	X	
Rodriguez et al.	1997	LSD		X
Moallem et al.	1997	CBD	X	
Garcia-Bojalil et al.	1998	CRD	X	
Moallem et al.	1999	CBD	X	
Moallem et al.	2000	CBD	X	
Umphrey et al.	2001	CBD	X	
Weiss and Wyatt	2004	LSD		X
DeFrain et al.	2005	CBD	X	
Garnsworthy et al.	2008	CBD	X	
Moallem et al.	2010	CRD	X	
Rico et al.	2014	LSD		X
Stoffel et al.	2015	LSD		X
de Souza and Lock	2018a	LSD		X
Ylioja et al.	2018	LSD		X

¹ LSD = Latin square design; SRD = single reversal design; CRD = complete randomized design; CBD = complete block design.

² Continuous = CRD, CBD; Change-over = LSD, SRD.

Supplemental Table S2. Descriptive statistics of variables according to experimental design in the data set.

Item	Change-Over							Continuous						
	n ¹		Overall					n ¹		Overall				
	CON	CSPF	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	CON	CSPF	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD
DMI, kg/d	17	17	23.2	22.6	16.0	29.5	3.54	31	37	21.4	21.7	16.2	25.0	2.74
Nutrient digestibility, %														
DM	11	11	65.5	65.6	61.1	69.9	2.70	7	7	64.8	65.2	55.8	68.6	3.25
CP	7	7	65.5	66.3	59.7	70.2	3.41	6	6	64.6	68.1	54.7	73.2	6.51
NDF	11	11	45.0	41.2	31.2	57.2	8.91	9	9	47.1	44.4	36.5	61.7	8.53
Yield, kg/d														
Milk	18	18	34.6	33.4	22.5	48.9	6.60	29	35	34.9	34.9	23.6	42.9	5.27
Fat	18	18	1.26	1.21	0.89	1.78	0.22	28	34	1.19	1.15	0.79	1.71	0.22
Protein	17	17	1.04	1.01	0.82	1.47	0.19	27	33	1.07	1.03	0.76	1.42	0.16
3.5% FCM ³	18	18	33.4	33.4	27.2	48.5	5.87	23	29	33.2	33.3	24.0	43.8	5.47
ECM ³	16	16	33.8	34.2	27.7	48.3	5.89	23	29	33.6	33.8	24.3	42.9	5.25
Milk content, g/100g														
Fat	18	18	3.57	3.57	2.80	5.19	0.62	34	37	3.42	3.36	2.67	4.48	0.36
Protein	17	17	3.15	3.09	2.88	3.95	0.26	32	35	3.01	3.00	2.55	3.69	0.22
BW, kg/d	8	8	591	606	562	718	45.7	15	19	598	616	526	745	55.3
Energy output ⁴ , Mcal/d														
Milk	16	16	24.6	23.1	19.2	33.5	3.85	28	31	23.1	22.8	16.6	28.2	3.06
Maintenance	8	8	9.23	9.77	11.1	9.60	0.54	15	19	8.78	9.89	11.4	9.64	0.66
Milk fatty acid yield ⁵ , g/d														
De novo	7	7	293	277	182	417	51.3	6	8	255	257	190	327	40.4
Mixed	8	8	461	538	288	587	60.0	7	9	354	340	281	439	45.6
Preformed	7	7	360	416	284	628	40.4	7	9	429	439	230	673	138
Milk fatty acid content ⁵ , g/100g														
De novo	7	7	22.1	21.9	17.5	25.7	2.80	6	8	23.5	23.9	15.8	34.0	5.48
Mixed	8	8	33.5	44.6	25.4	47.3	8.23	7	9	32.4	31.5	29.3	36.8	1.73
Preformed	7	7	27.8	32.9	25.6	41.4	4.58	7	9	38.7	39.7	23.9	50.1	9.70

¹ Number of treatment means of non-fat supplemented control diets (CON) or diets supplemented with calcium salts of palm fatty acids (CSPF).

² 3.5 % FCM = [(0.4324 × kg milk) + (16.216 × kg milk fat)] (NRC, 2001).

³ ECM = [(0.327 × kg milk) + (12.95 × kg milk fat) + (7.20 × kg milk protein)] (NRC, 2001).

⁴ Energy output to milk (Mcal/d) = [9.29 × fat (%) + 5.63 × true protein (%) + 3.95 × lactose (%)] (NRC, 2001); Energy output to maintenance (Mcal/d) = BW^{0.75} (kg) × 0.08 (NRC, 2001).

⁵ De novo fatty acids originate from mammary de novo synthesis (<16 carbons), preformed fatty acids originated from extraction from plasma (>16 carbons), and mixed fatty acids originate from both sources (C16:0 plus *cis*-9 C16:1).

Supplemental Table S3. Descriptive statistics of variables for non-fat supplemented control diets (CON) or diets supplemented with calcium salts of palm fatty acids (CSPF) in the data set.

Item	CON						CSPF					
	n ¹	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	n ¹	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD
DMI, kg/d	48	22.3	22.2	16.2	29.5	3.13	54	21.7	21.6	16.3	28.7	2.97
Nutrient												
DM	18	65.2	65.2	55.8	69.9	3.18	18	65.3	65.6	59.1	69.0	2.74
CP	13	64.6	65.9	54.8	70.8	5.35	13	65.6	67.1	54.7	73.2	5.83
NDF	20	45.1	43.0	31.2	59.30	9.11	20	46.7	44.3	33.4	61.7	8.73
FA ²	13	68.9	64.9	53.5	88.1	11.1	13	71.6	66.2	57.1	90.0	9.64
Yield, kg/d												
Milk	47	34.0	33.5	22.5	48.3	5.80	53	35.6	34.3	23.6	48.9	5.71
Fat	46	1.19	1.15	0.82	1.71	0.22	52	1.24	1.22	0.79	1.78	0.22
Protein	44	1.06	1.02	0.76	1.47	0.18	50	1.06	1.03	0.77	1.46	0.16
Lactose	11	1.73	1.64	1.10	2.31	0.39	12	1.75	1.69	1.20	2.37	0.34
3.5% FCM ³	41	33.9	32.7	24.6	47.5	5.51	47	35.2	33.5	24.0	48.5	5.67
ECM ⁴	39	33.7	33.1	21.2	47.6	5.85	45	34.8	33.8	22.4	48.3	5.85
ECM/DMI,	37	1.58	1.53	1.19	2.47	0.22	43	1.62	1.62	1.29	2.16	0.21
Milk Content,												
Fat	52	3.45	3.47	2.67	5.19	0.49	55	3.49	3.45	2.68	5.19	0.47
Protein	49	3.08	3.05	2.58	3.95	0.23	52	3.03	2.99	2.55	3.69	0.24
Lactose	14	4.79	4.83	4.56	4.97	0.13	15	4.81	4.81	4.52	5.06	0.15
BW, kg	23	599	612	530	745	54.5	27	591	612	526	742	51.2
BW change,	9	0.22	0.16	-	0.61	0.19	13	0.16	0.13	-	0.78	0.69
BCS	10	3.23	3.13	2.60	3.57	0.34	14	3.13	2.99	2.50	3.56	0.29
Energy												
Milk	44	23.0	22.8	17.0	32.6	3.34	47	23.9	23.0	16.6	33.5	3.42
Maintenance	23	9.64	9.84	8.83	11.4	0.65	27	9.59	9.84	8.78	11.4	0.61
Milk Fatty Acid Yield ⁶ , g/d												
De novo	13	297	288	225	416	48.1	15	256	250	250	182	46.4
Mixed	15	404	374	281	587	112	17	417	408	283	580	108
Preformed	14	370	380	299	601	112	16	414	440	233	673	129
Milk Fatty Acid Content ⁶ , g/100g												
De novo	13	24.8	25.0	18.8	34.0	3.74	15	20.8	20.8	15.8	30.3	4.60
Mixed	15	32.3	31.3	25.4	47.3	7.72	17	33.6	32.6	27.7	46.2	5.97
Preformed	14	31.2	32.2	23.9	46.0	8.10	16	34.1	36.2	24.8	50.1	8.26

¹Number of treatment means.

²Fatty acids.

³3.5 % FCM = [(0.4324 × kg milk) + (16.216 × kg milk fat)] (NRC, 2001).

⁴ECM = [(0.327 × kg milk) + (12.95 × kg milk fat) + (7.20 × kg milk protein)] (NRC, 2001).

⁵Energy output to milk (Mcal/d) = [9.29 × fat (%) + 5.63 × true protein (%) + 3.95 × lactose (%)] (NRC, 2001); Energy output to maintenance (Mcal/d) = BW^{0.75} (kg) × 0.08 (NRC, 2001).

⁶De novo fatty acids originate from mammary de novo synthesis (<16 carbons), preformed fatty acids originated from extraction from plasma (>16 carbons), and mixed fatty acids originate from both sources (C16:0 plus *cis*-9 C16:1).

Supplemental Table S4. Descriptive statistics of individual milk fatty acids (FA) for non-fat supplemented control diets (CON) or diets supplemented with calcium salts of palm fatty acids (CSPF) in the data set.

Item	CON						CSPF					
	n ¹	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	n ¹	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD
Milk FA Yield, g/100g												
C4:0	9	40.2	35.3	28.7	55.1	8.74	11	42.6	36.3	30.9	60.6	7.69
C6:0	13	26.7	24.8	16.3	36.5	7.65	15	24.7	24.1	14.2	35.8	5.84
C8:0	13	16.5	16.5	11.3	21.7	4.01	15	14.1	13.5	7.80	19.2	3.38
C10:0	13	38.5	36.5	23.8	51.6	9.13	15	30.6	27.1	14.1	42.5	8.43
C12:0	13	44.6	40.8	29.7	58.5	8.70	15	34.3	33.5	18.2	47.2	8.47
C14:0	13	141	143	107	193	22.2	15	118	119	77.4	170	19.3
C14:1	8	13.1	12.2	10.3	15.9	2.36	8	10.1	9.39	8.51	11.7	1.20
C16:0	15	390	354	269	560	101	17	403	400	267	559	95.3
C16:1	11	22.2	19.9	19.1	26.8	3.17	11	21.3	20.4	18.5	25.2	2.78
C18:0	14	122	108	72.3	189	36.9	16	127	119	72.7	195	34.7
C18:1	11	247	243	166	359	53.2	11	313	292	235	437	54.1
C18:2	14	39.7	30.2	20.5	64.1	14.5	16	41.7	31.1	18.3	62.4	13.5
C18:3	7	6.99	6.04	2.88	13.8	3.60	9	7.24	5.78	3.89	12.9	2.90
Milk FA Content, g/100g												
C4:0	9	3.24	2.85	2.49	4.13	0.68	11	3.33	3.59	2.53	4.20	0.65
C6:0	13	2.19	2.23	1.37	3.16	0.68	15	2.03	2.00	1.15	2.79	0.60
C8:0	13	1.33	1.31	0.91	1.98	0.38	15	1.13	1.07	0.68	1.78	0.38
C10:0	13	3.07	2.94	2.09	5.01	0.88	15	2.38	2.15	1.36	4.30	0.98
C12:0	13	3.63	3.57	2.61	5.99	0.87	15	2.68	2.66	1.75	5.03	1.02
C14:0	13	11.6	12.0	9.41	13.9	1.22	15	9.62	10.1	7.45	12.7	1.59
C14:1	8	0.97	1.08	0.80	1.50	0.23	8	0.74	0.79	0.65	0.95	0.11
C16:0	15	31.3	29.8	23.6	45.6	7.14	17	32.3	31.7	25.7	44.6	5.84
C16:1	11	1.85	1.80	1.50	2.12	0.19	11	1.77	1.76	1.40	2.02	0.22
C18:0	14	10.0	9.37	7.24	17.8	2.94	16	10.2	9.61	7.04	16.7	2.48
C18:1	11	21.3	22.1	14.9	27.1	4.30	11	26.2	24.8	19.5	32.5	4.12
C18:2	14	3.38	2.58	1.95	5.83	1.33	16	3.39	2.44	1.95	5.93	1.30
C18:3	7	0.55	0.53	0.30	1.12	0.29	9	0.51	0.45	0.35	0.99	0.20

¹Number of treatment means.

Supplemental Table S5, Meta.2. Milk fatty acid (FA) yields and concentrations of cows fed non-fat supplemented control diets (CON) or diets supplemented with calcium salts of palm fatty acids (CSPF).

Item	Mean difference		n ²	Variance ³		P-value ⁴
	Estimate ¹	SE		$\hat{\sigma}_s$	$\hat{\sigma}_e$	
Milk FA Yield, g/d						
C4:0	2.42	2.42	5(20)	0.10	0.01	0.12
C6:0	-2.03	0.79	7(28)	0.05	0.00	0.02
C8:0	-2.49	0.57	7(28)	13.3	2.31	<0.01
C10:0	-7.96	1.55	7(28)	0.07	0.17	<0.01
C12:0	-10.2	1.70	7(28)	0.07	0.02	<0.01
C14:0	-22.3	3.31	7(28)	0.71	0.08	<0.01
C14:1	-3.07	0.95	4(16)	0.00	3.67	<0.01
C16:0	13.7	5.23	9(32)	8.26	0.21	0.02
C16:1	-0.84	1.06	6(22)	0.01	0.01	0.44
C18:0	4.62	3.60	8(30)	1.37	0.60	0.22
C18:1	66.0	17.8	8(22)	1.93	1.75	<0.01
C18:2	2.08	1.90	8(30)	0.18	0.03	0.29
C18:3	0.24	0.37	5(16)	11.8	0.53	0.53
Milk FA Content, g/100g						
C4:0	0.08	0.03	5(20)	0.35	0.01	0.03
C6:0	-0.17	0.04	7(28)	0.27	0.01	<0.01
C8:0	-0.19	0.03	7(28)	0.10	0.01	<0.01
C10:0	-0.69	0.12	7(28)	0.52	0.11	<0.01
C12:0	-0.95	0.16	7(28)	0.47	0.17	<0.01
C14:0	-2.06	0.28	7(28)	1.75	0.36	<0.01
C14:1	-0.23	0.05	4(16)	0.01	0.01	<0.01
C16:0	1.02	0.45	9(32)	28.0	0.87	0.05
C16:1	-0.08	0.08	6(22)	0.00	0.04	0.38
C18:0	0.25	0.29	8(30)	4.16	0.39	0.40
C18:1	4.81	1.03	8(22)	13.38	5.91	<0.01
C18:2	0.01	0.08	8(30)	1.47	0.05	0.90
C18:3	-0.03	0.03	5(16)	0.04	0.00	0.39

¹ Difference between treatments (CSPF – CON).

² Number of studies (overall number of treatment means). More information in Supplementary Table 4.

³ $\hat{\sigma}_s$ = square root of the estimated study variance; $\hat{\sigma}_e$ = square root of the estimated residual variance.

⁴ P-values associated with the effects of CON vs. CSPF.

Supplemental Table S6, Meta.3. Milk fatty acid (FA) yields and concentrations of cows for each 1-percentage-unit increase of calcium salts of palm fatty acids (CSPF) in diet dry matter.

Item	Inclusion/1%DM ¹		n ²	Variance ³		P-value ⁴
	CSPF	SEM		$\hat{\sigma}_s$	$\hat{\sigma}_e$	CSPF/1%DM
Milk FA Yield, g/d						
C4:0	0.74	0.74	5(11)	0.08	0.08	0.36
C6:0	-1.00	0.37	7(15)	1.20	1.94	0.03
C8:0	-1.27	0.29	7(15)	1.08	1.28	<0.01
C10:0	-3.81	0.66	7(15)	0.07	0.10	<0.01
C12:0	-4.85	0.68	7(15)	0.07	0.11	<0.01
C14:0	-10.1	1.24	7(15)	0.00	0.32	<0.01
C14:1	-1.32	0.47	4(8)	0.04	0.06	0.03
C16:0	10.56	3.94	9(17)	0.41	0.41	0.03
C16:1	-0.33	0.20	6(11)	0.00	0.05	0.18
C18:0	2.16	1.41	8(16)	0.18	0.19	0.18
C18:1	24.2	4.80	8(17)	0.74	0.17	0.01
C18:2	0.87	0.53	8(16)	0.06	0.09	0.14
C18:3	0.20	0.21	5(9)	0.35	0.88	0.42
Milk FA Content, g/100g						
C4:0	0.02	0.03	5(11)	0.10	0.08	0.55
C6:0	-0.10	0.03	7(15)	0.11	0.06	0.01
C8:0	-0.11	0.02	7(15)	0.09	0.05	<0.01
C10:0	-0.33	0.04	7(15)	0.16	0.10	<0.01
C12:0	-0.42	0.04	7(15)	0.17	0.13	<0.01
C14:0	-0.95	0.06	7(15)	0.18	0.36	<0.01
C14:1	-0.09	0.01	4(8)	0.01	0.05	<0.01
C16:0	0.56	0.19	9(17)	1.16	0.41	0.02
C16:1	-0.02	0.03	6(11)	0.11	0.07	0.45
C18:0	0.03	0.10	8(16)	0.51	0.34	0.76
C18:1	1.88	0.22	8(17)	0.82	0.50	<0.01
C18:2	0.01	0.01	8(16)	0.03	0.10	0.68
C18:3	-0.02	0.02	5(9)	0.06	0.02	0.44

¹ Supplementations of calcium salts of palm fatty acids (CSPF) per 1-percentage-unit increase in diet DM.

² Number of studies (the resulting number of observations obtained from the difference between CSPF diet means minus control diet [CON] means used in the meta-regression). More information in Supplementary Table 4.

³ $\hat{\sigma}_s$ = square root of the estimated study variance; $\hat{\sigma}_e$ = square root of the estimated residual variance.

⁴ P-values were used to test the linear effect of the supplementation of CSPF per 1-percentage-unit increase in diet DM.

*We reviewed citations from previous reviews related to calcium salts of palm fatty acids (CSPF) supplementation: Firkins and Eastridge, 1994; Allen, 2000; Loftén and Cornelius, 2004; Onetti and Grummer, 2004; Rabiee et al., 2012; Loftén et al. 2014; Boerman et al., 2015; Dórea and Armentano, 2017; Dórea et al., 2017; Palmquist and Jenkins, 2017; Weld and Armentano, 2017.

**Papers were searched for in electronic databases (Scirus, CAB, Cambridge University Press, Elsevier, Google Scholar, PubMed, Science Direct, and Springer) and in the search engines of Animal Feed Science and Technology, Animal Production Science, Animal, Brazilian Journal of Animal Science, Journal of Animal Physiology and Animal Nutrition, Journal of Animal Science, Journal of Dairy Research, Journal of Dairy Science, Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture, Livestock Science, and The Professional Animal Scientist.

***Main reasons for exclusion were: 1) CSPF inclusion > 3% diet DM, 2) absence of [non-fat supplemented control diets](#), 3) inclusion of other fat supplements in addition to CSPF, and 4) studies using fat supplements rather than CSPF.

Supplemental Figure S1. The PRISMA flow diagram from the initial search and screening to the final selection of studies included for the meta-analysis and meta-regression on the effects of CSPF on nutrient digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows (Page et al., 2021; <http://www.prisma-statement.org/PRISMAStatement/FlowDiagram>).

Supplemental Figure S2. A. Standard Funnel plots for some of the key responses analyzed (Sterne and Harbord, 2004; Rabiee et al., 2012). **B.** Contour-Enhanced Funnel Plot for some of the key responses analyzed. The white region (unshaded) region in the middle corresponds to P -values greater than 0.10, the dark gray-shaded region corresponds to P -values between 0.10 and 0.05, the medium gray-shaded region corresponds to P -values between 0.05 and 0.01, and the region outside of the funnel corresponds to P -values below 0.01 (Sterne and Egger, 2001; Peters et al., 2008; https://www.metafor-project.org/doku.php/plots:contour_enhanced_funnel_plot).